

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B395
Date: 14 Aug 2008
Take Off: 10:30:20
Landing: 15:46:17
Flight Time 5h 15m 57s

Campaign: Potential Vorticity Anomaly Flight

Operating Area: West of Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Andreas Keil	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	David Devlin	Met Office	
6	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				

Flight Track:

B395 Track 14-AUG-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B395
 Date: 14/8/08
 Project: PV
 Location: West Of Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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101845		Engine Start	0.38 kft	123	
102231		taxy	0.38 kft	123	
103020		T/O	0.96 kft	228	from Cranfield
110522		bbr exposed	24.0 kft	329	
113959	114200	Run 1.1	25.9 - 26.0 kft	166	
114253	114453	Run 1.2	26.0 - 25.9 kft	269	
114557	114958	Run 1.3	25.9 - 26.0 kft	349	
115106	115506	Run 1.4	25.9 kft	088	
115611	120212	Run 1.5	25.9 kft	173	
120320	120926	Run 1.6	25.9 kft	266	
121031	121828	Run 1.7	26.0 - 25.9 kft	353	
121929	122729	Run 1.8	25.9 kft	085 1	
122729	123305	Profile 1	25.9 - 30.0 kft	082 1	
123320	123526	Run 2.1	30.0 kft	175	
123635	123833	Run 2.2	30.0 kft	264	
123937	124335	Run 2.3	30.0 kft	352	
124449	124846	Run 2.4	30.0 kft	084	
124953	125554	Run 2.5	30.0 kft	173	
125700	130301	Run 2.6	30.0 kft	266	
130408	131208	Run 2.7	30.0 kft	353	
131315	132126	Run 2.8	30.0 kft	087	
131324		Sonde 1	30.0 kft	085	
132437	132647	Profile 2	30.0 - 32.0 kft	225	
133936	134428	Profile 3	32.2 - 34.0 kft	202	
134924	135124	Run 3.1	34.0 kft	177	
135232	135435	Run 3.2	34.0 kft	269	
135545	135945	Run 3.3	34.0 kft	353	
140100	140455	Run 3.4	34.0 kft	083	
140605	141204	Run 3.5	34.0 kft	174	
141313	141913	Run 3.6	34.0 kft	265	
142017	142818	Run 3.7	34.0 kft	354	
142927	143726	Run 3.8	34.0 kft	084	
143839	143935	Profile 4	34.0 - 35.0 kft	185	
144222		Sonde 2	35.0 kft	175	
154617		Land	0.38 kft	215	at Cranfield

B395 Track 14-AUG-08

PV anomaly Sortie brief - B395 – 14th Aug 2008

Aim

Make measurements of wind field and thermodynamic structure of the atmosphere within an area predicted to have negative values of Potential Vorticity (PV). PV anomalies in the upper troposphere contribute to the development of synoptic weather systems and can be very influential in the evolution of forecasts. Areas of negative PV often occur in the Met Office model behind fronts but is not clear whether these are truly a feature of the atmosphere or a feature of the model's behaviour.

Weather

An area of negative PV is forecast to the west of Scotland, centred around 250hPa level. There is no preference for flying in clear sky or cloud.

Operating region

West of Scotland (within 55-58N, 4-11W; no flying west of 10W needed).
Centre of PV anomaly is forecast to be at **56N, 8W** at 1300 local time.

Clearances

Clearances will be required for dropping sondes over the operating region.

Spiral pattern

Turns of 90 degrees should take approx 30 secs, crossing roughly a 20Km box should take about 2mins. Including the profile ascent this pattern should take 50mins. The orientation of the pattern is largely irrelevant so a N-S, E-W orientation seems the easiest to manage. Science speed is preferred although if time constraints occur at the end then a brief acceleration before the last profile to FL350 would be OK.

	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	Take off from Cranfield at 1130 local time		0
2	Transit at high level to operating region. Aim to arrive at the forecast centre of the PV anomaly at FL260 on a heading of due North.	90	90
3	Perform a spiral pattern at FL260 starting from the centre of the PV anomaly. For spiral flying: Fly segments of 2 min (=2 min for starting leg, 10 min for last leg). Fly headings, not tracks. (means drifting with air mass)	45	135
4	Profile ascent to FL300 at 1000ft/min returning to pre-calculated shifted centre of PV anomaly (20nm miles shift eastwards) aiming to start a second spiral pattern on a southwards heading. [Turn diagram upside down.]	5	140
5	Perform a spiral pattern at FL300 starting from the centre of the PV anomaly.	45	185
6	Drop 1st sonde at the start of the last leg		
7	Profile ascent to FL340 at 1000ft/min and return aircraft to the shifted centre of PV anomaly (about 20 nm eastwards) aiming to start a 3 rd spiral pattern on a northwards heading.	5	190

8	Perform a spiral pattern at FL340 starting from the centre of the PV anomaly (initial heading should be northwards). [Turn diagram back again.] <i>If time runs out here then the spiral can be shortened by missing out the western most part of the spiral.</i>	45	235
9	Climb to maximum FL350 and drop a 2nd sonde as close to the centre of the PV anomaly as possible.	5	240
10	Transit back to Cranfield	60	300

————— Legs of spiral pattern
 - - - - - Track during profile ascents

Around
 20Km =
 ← 2mins →

Debrief B395 - PV anomaly

Mission Scientist: Andreas Keil
Principle Investigator: Dave Devlin

Date: 14 Aug 2008
Airfield: Cranfield
T/O: 11:30 local

Background/Goal

The aim was to make measurements of wind field and thermodynamic structure of the atmosphere within an area predicted to have negative values of Potential Vorticity (PV). PV anomalies in the upper troposphere contribute to the development of synoptic weather systems and can be very influential in the evolution of forecasts. Areas of negative PV often occur in the Met Office model behind fronts but is not clear whether these are truly a feature of the atmosphere or a feature of the model's behaviour.

Weather

An area of negative PV was forecast to the west of Scotland, centred around 250hPa level. There was no preference for flying in clear sky or cloud. Weather conditions encountered matched nicely with the forecast. There were varying amounts of low level clouds (Sc, Cu) and Cirrus during the flight, but no clouds at the flight levels we were operating at.

Operating region

West of Scotland within 55-57N, 6-9W, starting at the centre of PV anomaly, which had been forecast to be at **56N, 8W** at about 1300 local time, then drifting eastwards with the wind.

Sortie

3 Spiral Patterns (see Figure 1, which you have to turn on its top to get South-North orientation as usual) were performed at FL 260, 300, and 340. Two sondes were dropped from FL300 and from FL350. See Mission Scientist's flight log and print out of flight tracks for details. Keep in mind that all sorties were flown to allow drifting with the air mass, i.e. all legs were flown on constant heading (not on constant track) and flight legs were defined by an exact time (2, 4, 6 or 8 minutes), not by distance {easterly winds means that W→E tracks are longer than e.g. E→W or N→S tracks}.

Summary

For the first time a PV anomaly sortie was flown. All manoeuvres were performed as planned before. Between spiral 2 and 3 some waiting manoeuvres were forced by air traffic control, but sufficient contingency had been planned in to still perform the full sortie and to achieve all objectives.

Figure 1: Spiral Pattern as flown.

————— Legs of spiral pattern

- - - - - Track during profile ascents

Around
20Km =
2mins

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.395** Date 14/8/08
 FAAM © 2004 "Negative for Italy"

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30		(Rft)	(0)		Cransfield T/O
					Transit to operating area (56N/8W)
					- wind, T, RH measurements OK!
					- HOPE vert. Vorticity <u>not</u> working + wind
(17:39)					Start Spirale I at FL240
11:30:39	1/1	25.9	173	56N/8W	2 min. ↓ (N → S) / p = 360 mb
11:42:53	1/2	"	261		2 min. ← (E → W)
11:45:57	1/3	"	355		4 min. ↑ (S → N)
11:49:58	1/4	"	85		4 min. → (W → E)
11:56:11	1/5	"	172		6 min. ↓
12:03:20	1/6	"	261		6 min. ←
12:10:31	1/7	"	356		8 min. ↑
12:19:29	1/8	"	84		8 min. → / End 1
					exact timings of legs
12:20					- climbing to FL300
					- clouds: low, scattered Sc; some Ci above
(12:33)					Start Spirale II at FL300
12:33:05	2/1	30.0	174	56N/7.5W	2 min. ↓ / p = 300 mb
12:36:35	2/2	"	262		2 min. ←
12:39:37	2/3	"	354		4 min. ↑
12:44:49	2/4	"	84		4 min. →
12:49:50	2/5	"	173		6 min. ↓
12:57:00	2/6	"	261		6 min. ←
13:04:08	2/7	"	354		8 min. ↑
13:13:15	2/8	"			8 min. → + 13:13:20 Sonde dropped

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 395** Date 14/8/08
 FAAM © 2004 "Negative Forticity"

Page 2 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:22					- climbing to FL340
					[- some waiting loops forced by air traffic control at FL320]
					- so/cn below, no cloud above
<u>13:49</u>					Start of SPIRAL E III at FL340
13:49:24	3/1	34.0	175	56N/7W	2 min ↓
13:52:32	3/2	"	266		2 min ←
13:55:45	3/3	"	356		4 min ↑
14:01:00	3/4	"	83		4 min →
14:07:00	3/5	"			6 min ↓
14:13:15	3/6	"			6 min ←
14:21:00	3/7	"			8 min ↑
14:29:27	3/8	"			8 min → / End 3
14:38					- climbing to 35k ft (FL350)
14:42		35.0		56N/62W	⊖ <u>Sonde Dropped</u> 14:42:30 data OK
14:43					Negative Forticity mission accomplished Finish of Science flying Σ = - 3 spirals at 240/300/340 FL - 2 sondes dropped from FL 300 and 350 - fully successful flight
14:45					Transit back to Cranfield
16:					LANDING //

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 395

Date: 14/08/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:40:00																Good noise data on FFSSP	
																Signal value set at 25	
10:50:																In cloud	
																SID2 detector voltage low!	
11:15																FFSSP noise test aborted – went into cloud!	
11:19	2	0.07														FFSSP noise test	
11:20	1	0.07														FFSSP noise test	
11:40:00																Start Run 1.1 @ FL260	
11:41:00	3	0.08	124		Off												
11:42:01																End of Run 1.1	
11:42:54																Start Run 1.2 @ FL260	
11:43:00	5	0.09															
11:44:54																End of Run 1.2	
11:45:58																Start Run 1.3 @ FL260	
11:46:00	6	0.08															
11:48:00	7	0.08															
11:49:58																End of Run 1.3	
11:51:06																Start Run 1.4 @ FL260	
11:52:00	5	0.08															
11:54:00	5	0.08															
11:55:07																End of Run 1.4	
11:56:11																Start Run 1.5 @ FL260	
11:57:00	4	0.08															
11:59:00	5	0.08															
12:01:00	7	0.09															
12:02:05																End of Run 1.5	
12:03:21																Start Run 1.6 @ FL260	
12:04:00	7	0.08															
12:06:00	4	0.08															
12:08:00	5	0.08															
12:09:23																End of Run 1.6	
12:10:25																Start Run 1.7 @ FL260	
12:11:00	5	0.08															
12:13:00	8	0.08															
12:15:00	8	0.08	125														
12:17:00	6	0.08															
12:18:23																End of Run 1.7	
12:19:29																Start Run 1.8 @ FL260	
12:20:00	4	0.07															
12:22:00	5	0.09															
12:24:00	6	0.09															
12:26:00	5	0.09															
12:27:32																End of Run 1.8 & Start P1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.1V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 32mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 395

Date: 14/08/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:29:04	3	0.10														FL270	
12:30:15	6	0.08														FL280	
12:31:40	6	0.08														FL290	
12:33:05																End of P1 @ FL300	
12:33:20																Start Run 2.1 @ FL300	
12:34:00	6	0.09															
12:35:19																End of Run 2.1	
12:35:55																Start Run 2.2 @ FL300	
12:36:35																	
12:37:00	5	0.09															
12:38:31																End of Run 2.2	
12:39:34																Start Run 2.3 @ FL300	
12:40:00	5	0.08															
12:42:00	5	0.08															
12:43:36																End of Run 2.3	
12:44:45																Start Run 2.4 @ FL300	
12:45:00	3	0.10	126														
12:47:00	3	0.10	127			1	75								11		
12:48:46																End of Run 2.4	
12:49:56																Start Run 2.5 @ FL300	
12:50:00	4	0.08															
12:52:00	6	0.09															
12:54:00	7	0.08															
12:55:55																End of Run 2.5	
12:57:05																Start Run 2.6 @ FL300	
12:58:00	10	0.07															
13:00:00	7	0.08															
13:02:00	4	0.07															
13:03:02																End of Run 2.6	
13:04:08																Start Run 2.7 @ FL300	
13:05:00	5	0.08															
13:07:00	5	0.08															
13:09:00	3	0.08															
13:11:00	5	0.08															
13:12:08																End of Run 2.7	
13:13:18																Start Run 2.8 @ FL300	
13:14:00	4	0.07															
13:16:00	3	0.08	129			5	100								10		
13:18:00	10	0.11	130			40	175								10		
13:20:00	3	0.08	132			15	175								10		
13:21:26																End of Run 2.8	
13:24:41																Start Profile 2 from FL300	
13:25:50	3	0.13														FL310	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.1V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 32mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 395

Date: 14/08/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:26:47	3	0.08														End of P2 @ FL320	
13:39:44																Start P3 from FL320	
13:41:35	3	0.06														FL330	
13:44:31	2	0.06														End of P2 @ @ FL340	
13:49:26																Start Run 3.1 @ FL340	
13:50:00	5	0.07	427														
13:51:30																End of Run 3.1	
13:52:39																Start Run 3.2 @ FL340	
13:53:00	3	0.07	428													Signal setting allowing just some noise in @ 26 When value = 28 average	
13:54:34																End of Run 3.2	
13:55:49																Start Run 3.3 @ FL340	
13:56:00	1	0.05	429														
13:58:00	2	0.06															
13:59:48																End of Run 3.3	
14:00:58																Start Run 3.4 @ FL340	
14:01:00	2	0.04															
14:03:00	2	0.04	430														
14:04:57																End of Run 3.4	
14:06:11																Start Run 3.5 @ FL340	
14:07:00	4	0.06															
14:09:00	3	0.08	431														
14:11:00	3	0.09															
14:12:03																End of Run 3.5	
14:13:13																Start Run 3.6 @ FL340	
14:14:00	3	0.07															
14:16:00	3	0.07															
14:18:00	4	0.08	432														
14:19:30																End of Run 3.6	
14:20:18																Start Run 3.7 @ FL340	
14:21:00	3	0.07															
14:23:00	3	0.06															
14:25:00	3	0.06															
14:27:00	3	0.08															
14:28:20																End of Run 3.7	
14:29:31																Start Run 3.8 @ FL340	
14:30:00	2	0.07															
14:32:00	1	0.07															
14:34:00	2	0.06															
14:36:00	2	0.06															
14:37:29																End of Run 3.8	
14:38:40																Start Profile 4 from FL340	
14:39:37	2	0.06														End of P4	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.1V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 32mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CVI log

8/14/08 9:25:30 AM test flight to assess TAS and Tamb feed
8/14/08 9:25:43 AM will be turned off at ~10kft

Flight:

B395

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B395

Date: 14/8/08

Instruments

1.

Non Core:

SID2 not working still

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Flight B395 14:48:02

Heading 119 deg Speed 361 knots Height 27.0kft Press 343mb

Lat 55°30.0'N Long 5°36.0'W Wind 182 ms-1/ 359 deg

Temp -41.37C Dewpoint -46.03C

From 10:34:58 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -5.65 deg (+ve E)
GIN LATITUDE 55.51 deg (+ve N)

B395 lap 1, 2 & 3 screengrab

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B395:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
CPI log	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

AMS - not yet fitted

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	08 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_113618_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_123618_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_133618_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_143618_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_113610_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_123610_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_133610_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_143610_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_113606_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_123606_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_133606_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_143606_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_113614_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_123614_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_133614_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080814_r0_b395_143614_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.